

was most popular in the dry and intermediate zones for more than a decade. But in the low country wet zone it performed poorly because of disease, insect, climatic, and soil problems. Similar problems have caused the improved varieties such as BG11-11 and BG90-2 to perform poorly in the low country wet zone.

Until recently, the general opinion was that the area had low potential for rice. But the problems, particularly iron toxicity in mineral soils, were overemphasized.

The situation became clearer with the initiation of land classification of the wet zone. After problem areas were isolated, we could determine priorities. We have dropped the concept of releasing one variety to cover the entire area. Our present breeding program is geared to

breed specific varieties to overcome problems peculiar to the following specific conditions: 1) tolerance for flash floods, 2) ability of seed to germinate under standing water, 3) rapid seedling growth, 4) ability to compete with weeds, 5) tolerance for adverse soils, 6) resistance to diseases and insects, 7) resistance to storage pests, 8) palatability, and 9) red pericarp.

Some of the local varieties screened and the traits peculiar to them follow:

- Muhudukiriyal — salinity tolerance
- Karamana, Molligoda, and Sula — ability to emerge through standing water
- Deverreddiri — tolerance for floods and iron toxicity
- Podiwee A-8 — resistance to storage pests
- Batapolayal — rapid seedling growth

The results of screening of early generation material for resistance to gall midge, thrips, and iron toxicity are encouraging. In 1978 we began to test our promising materials in farmers' fields of varying land classes.

From the 4 to 4.5-month age group, LD66 and BW78 have been released and successfully cultivated in the wet zone. BW100 awaits release. Although we have released varieties for successful cultivation in the mineral and half bog soil, we have yet to find an alternative to the local variety Deverreddiri, which is grown on about 10% of the rice area on the coastal floodplains.

In all modesty, we can state that we have contributed positively toward the goal of making our country self-sufficient in rice. ■

Importance of flag leaf area and grain-straw ratio in rice improvement

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The importance in rice yield improvement of physiological traits such as flag leaf area and grain-straw ratio was studied through statistical tools.

One hundred twenty rices were selected from the germplasm maintained at Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India. The strains were classified into four groups based on maturity period and plant height: early

short, late short, early tall, and late tall. Thirty varieties in each group were grown in a randomized block design with three replications. The usual cultural practices were followed. Data on flag leaf area, and grain-straw ratio were collected from 10 randomly selected plants/replication.

Flag leaf area and grain-straw ratio varied widely in all groups. Although the range can provide an estimate of variability in the germplasm, the coefficient of variability could be more reliable. The grain-straw ratio showed a high coefficient of genetic and phenotypic variability (see table). The flag leaf area also showed appreciable coefficient

of variation.

Heritability (which provides a basis for making selections based on the phenotypic performance) and expected genetic advance were high for both traits in all groups.

The study showed a strong positive correlation between yield and grain-straw ratio in the early short (0.5202) and the late tall group (0.6632) and only a positive correlation in the early tall (0.2305) and late short (0.3431) groups. The flag leaf area and yield were correlated positively and significantly in the early short group (0.4075) but only positively in the other groups (see table). ■

Statistical parameters for flag leaf area and grain-straw ratio in various rice cultures, Ludhiana, India, 1979.^a

	Early short		Late short		Early tall		Late tall	
	Flag leaf area (cm)	Grain-straw ratio	Flag leaf area (cm)	Grainstraw ratio	Flag leaf area (cm)	Grain-straw ratio	Flag leaf area (cm)	Grain-straw ratio
Mean ± SE	40.544 ± 3.219	0.872 ± 0.065	31.185 ± 2.142	0.802 ± 0.033	56.991 ± 4.118	0.466 ± 0.028	58.574 ± 3.144	0.441 ± 0.027
Range	24.14 – 59.61	0.33 – 1.30	25.54 – 62.47	0.31 – 1.20	25.99 – 83.21	0.31 – 0.61	31.33 – 90.50	0.15 – 0.75
Coefficient of phenotypic variation (%)	25.51	28.08	23.25	30.02	27.82	27.18	23.94	31.30
Heritability (%)	21.49	24.83	19.56	29.13	24.84	24.99	21.63	29.35
Expected genetic advance (as % of mean)	40.73	45.30	36.66	58.26	44.47	47.10	43.65	56.71
Phenotypic correlation with yield	0.4075*	0.5202**	0.1653	0.3431	0.4200*	0.2305	0.1868	0.6632**
Genotypic correlation with yield	0.4966	0.5233	0.1947	0.3919	0.5585	0.2846	0.2210	0.7635

^a*Significant at 5% level. **Significant at 1% level.